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Deliverable Abstract

The EOSC Focus project WP4 has played a crucial role in supporting the EOSC Association (EOSC-A) in the monitoring, reporting and evaluation of the EOSC- Partnership's progress towards the objectives set out in its Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). EOSC Focus Deliverable 4.3 refers to the results achieved between May 2023 and December 2023. These include the establishment of functional and effective routines for the annual monitoring and reporting of the Additional Activities by the EOSC-A members, and for the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR). This deliverable also describes the support provided in the compilation of the first biennial Full Monitoring Report (FMR) of the EOSC Partnership, and the progress towards the monitoring and reporting of impactful case studies. Additionally, it provides a summary of the information compiled in the different reporting activities and of the lessons learned regarding the monitoring exercises.

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Glossary/ Abbreviations

Glossary/Abbreviations	Definition
AA	Additional Activities
AAP	Additional Activities Plan
AAR	Additional Activities Report
BMR	Biennial Monitoring Report
CI	Common Indicators
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-SB_A	EOSC Steering Board Subgroup A (Monitoring)
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud-Association
FMR	Full Monitoring Report
HE	Horizon Europe
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MF	Monitoring Framework
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
PSIP	Partnership Specific Impact Pathway
SEP	Sustainable Exploitation Planning
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
WG	Working Group

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Executive Summary

The EOSC Co-Programmed Partnership has made significant progress towards achieving the objectives outlined in the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)¹. WP4 of the EOSC Focus project has played a crucial role in supporting the EOSC-Association (EOSC-A) in its monitoring and reporting activities, contributing to establish routines within the Partnership. Deliverable 4.3 reports the results of this support between May and December 2023.

The monitoring and reporting routines described include annual and biennial activities as outlined in the MoU. As part of this process, in Q2/Q3 2023, EOSC-A, with the support of EOSC Focus, run the AAR 2022 survey in order to validate the planned contributions reported the previous year, with a resulting final figure of € 292 million. In addition, AAP 2024 survey was also launched during Q2/Q3 2023 and the estimated contributions for 2024 totalled €345 million. Both figures were presented and approved by the 5th Partnership Board meeting in December 2023. The total reported and planned contributions for 2022-2024 reach nearly €1 billion, almost doubling EOSC-A's original contribution plan for the entire EOSC Partnership duration (2021-2030).

The biennial reporting process begins with the collection of data for the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR) published by the European Commission. This includes monitoring indicators common for Horizon Europe partnerships through the Common Indicators (CI) survey, followed by the submission of the Partnership-specific Fiche and Partnership Full Monitoring Report (FMR).

The 2023 Common Indicators survey highlighted substantial achievements by the EOSC Partnership, including €532.7 million of in-kind contributions and an additional investment of approximately €2.7 billion. The Partnership demonstrated a focus on digitalisation, with 65% of its target achieved by August 2023.

The EOSC Partnership Fiche offered an overview of the Partnership's vision, mission, and impact pathways. Noteworthy efforts were invested in redesigning the Partnership-Specific Impact Pathways (PSIPs) and selecting Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that align with Horizon Europe Key Impact Pathways.

The first biennial EOSC Partnership FMR for the period June 2021 to June 2023 was also submitted, which includes a compendium of the information from the various reporting strands, such as the BMR and the Common Indicators submissions, while providing insights into the additionality, directionality, and the overall functioning of the Partnership.

Impact assessment is also an important part of the Partnership's periodic reporting, to be exemplified by EOSC-related impact case studies. The mining of case studies from the AAR 2022 provided relevant examples of activities addressing global societal challenges, such as the COVID-19 pandemic response, which were included in the BMR and FMR reports.

Looking ahead, the report outlines the establishment of the Horizon Europe EOSC Impact Working Group, emphasising its role in supporting the demonstration of EOSC's value through use cases examples. In the second semester of 2023, the idea of organising the EOSC Winter School 2024 took shape and a session on the "Sustainable Exploitation of HE projects' Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for Impact" was prepared.

¹ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC_Memorandum_30_July_2021.pdf

In conclusion, this report provides an overview of the achievements of the EOSC Partnership, and the EOSC Focus project has effectively supported EOSC-A in its monitoring and reporting activities, demonstrating a continued commitment to these efforts in the future.

1. Introduction

In June 2021, the Horizon Europe Co-Programmed Partnership for EOSC was established by the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)¹ between the European Union (EU), represented by the European Commission (EC) and the EOSC Association (EOSC-A), to define a coordinated approach in investments and initiatives for the realisation of the objectives set out in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)²: 1) to ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'; 2) to ensure that standards are defined, and services and tools developed, to enable researchers to find, access, reuse/combine and reproduce data from all research areas—i.e. data that comply with the FAIR principles³; and: 3) to establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results.

With this MoU, the EC commits to €490 million in Horizon Europe actions from 2021 to 2030, while the EOSC-A and its Members commit to deliver a comparable volume of actions as in-kind additional activities (AAs) in the same period.

1.1. The Monitoring and Evaluation Framework of the EOSC Partnership

The activities of the Partnership are continuously monitored and periodically reported for evaluation by the EC, during the whole duration of the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Framework Programme. The periodic evaluation consists of both annual and biennial monitoring and reporting activities, which differ in terms of goal and scope:

- Annual Monitoring and Reporting Activity:
 - Report of the EOSC-A Members' forecast contributions (ex-ante), through the establishment of the annual **Additional Activities Plan (AAP)**;
 - Report on the EOSC-A Members' consumptive contributions (ex-post), through the **Additional Activities Report (AAR)**.
- Biennial Reporting Activity (2021, 2023, 2025, 2027):
 - **Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR)** including indicators common to all Horizon Europe partnerships;
 - The progress of the EOSC Partnership towards its objectives and expected impacts against the **Key Performance Indicators** set out in the EOSC Partnership Monitoring Framework⁴;
 - **Full Monitoring Report (FMR)** covering the following aspects:
 - Functioning of the Partnership (additionality, directionality, international visibility and positioning, transparency and openness, coherence, and synergies);
 - Agreed and actual contributions;
 - Investments in operational activities;
 - Structured and representative 'impact case studies' (success stories).

² https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

³ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ <https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/Monitoring%20Framework.pdf>

1.2. Scope of this deliverable

This deliverable continues the work initiated in the EOSC Focus D4.2: “Annual Report Published by EOSC-A & Monitoring Framework Revision (First release)”, of May 2023⁵, and presents the results of the support by EOSC Focus (WP4) to the EOSC Partnership monitoring and reporting activities from May until December 2023. In particular, this deliverable aims to:

- report on the forecast contributions by the EOSC-A Members for 2024, in terms of the Additional Activities Plan 2024 (AAP 2024);
- report on the consumptive contributions by the EOSC-A Members for 2022, in terms of the Additional Activities Report 2022 (AAR 2022);
- describe the overall progress of the EOSC European Partnership, as emerged through its biennial reporting activities, including BMR which consists of the Common Indicators (CI) survey, the EOSC Partnership Fiche, and the Full Monitoring Report (FMR);
- describe the work initiated by WP4 to support:
 - the monitoring of the impact generated by the EOSC Partnership (EOSC Macro-Roadmap; impact case studies collection template);
 - the realisation of the EOSC Partnership impact potential, through the activities connected with the establishment of the HE Impact Working Group;
- reflect on the lessons learnt, and prepare for the next steps.

2. Monitoring and Reporting activities

2.1. Additional Activities Plan 2024 (AAP 2024)

In the MoU, EOSC-A committed to contribute €500 million in kind to the objectives of the EOSC Partnership over the lifetime of the MoU (2021-2030). This is measured annually by the AAP, which is an ex-ante plan along nine high-level categories that has to be approved by the EOSC Partnership Board prior to its implementation.

The AAP 2024 survey was conducted by the EOSC-A with the support of EOSC Focus WP4 in Q2/Q3 2023 on the EUSurvey platform⁶ to report on forecasted activities for the year 2024. Eighty-three members completed the survey, representing twenty-three countries in Europe such as The Netherlands, Croatia and Slovakia. 59% of respondents came from Research Performing Organisations, 29% were Service Providers, 8% Research Funding Organisations and 4% came from other type of organisations. Most respondents came from public organisations (86%). The categories that EOSC-A members planned to invest more into during 2024 are the following: Category 1 - Support to additional R&I planned investment, €127 million; Category 5 - Training & skills development, €36 million and Category 7 - Supporting ecosystem development, €67 million.

The survey comprised three Sections:

- Section 1 “Organisation Profile”
- Section 2 “Additional Activities”, which followed the nine main categories provided by the EC to all HE projects. Under each category there was a further breakdown into activity types, as agreed with the EC. For each activity type, EOSC-A Members reported the number of Full-Time Equivalents (FTEs) and the monetary value (€) of the described activities (including the value

⁵ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20230517_D4.2_3_GS_PendingREA.pdf

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

of FTEs), along with a description of the activities, highlighting their relevance to EOSC. An optional standard conversion factor of 100 000,00 Euro per 1 FTE (i.e. 1 FTE = 100 000,00 EURO/YEAR) was applied to calculate the monetary value of the reported FTE contributions.

- Section 3 covered case studies.

The AAP (as well as the AAR survey, described in the Section 2.2) changed slightly from 2022 to 2024. In the 2022 survey there was an activity type under each category for “other activities”; after consulting the EC, this was merged into another activity type within the same category. Therefore, the “other” option would only be available once under category 9. Additionally, Activities 7.9 and 7.10, which refer to the strategic and operational alignment with other structures and projects at international and national level respectively, have been merged into one. Finally, given the significance of demonstrating the practical applications of EOSC, the 2024 AAP survey invited EOSC-A members to provide more information on these activities. The aim was to gather more information on the specific impact of these activities, not only in terms of the number of FTEs and financial contributions, but also in terms of the specific areas impacted. The AAP 2024 survey questionnaire is available on the EOSC-A website⁷.

To facilitate respondents' submissions, EOSC-A, with the support of EOSC Focus WP4, conducted a series of online training sessions for the AAP and AAR surveys. These sessions aimed to assist Members in navigating the AAP 2024 and AAR 2022 questionnaires and were accessible through the provided booking web form. Five training sessions were held on 28 and 30 June, 6 July, and 23 and 29 August. The training content, including a detailed presentation, covered various aspects crucial to the completion of the survey. To further support participants, training materials, including the presentation in PDF format⁸, were shared on the EOSC-A website. The presentation covered key issues such as the Memorandum of Understanding between the EU and EOSC-A, Definition of Additional Activities (AAs), Monitoring & Reporting of AAs, Categories of AAs, The Survey on Additional Activities Plan 2024 and Report on AAP 2022, General improvements, Survey Structure, Survey Guidance, Live demonstration, Background information, and Frequently Asked Questions.

Table 1 summarises the AAP 2024 survey results (approved by the 5th Partnership Board meeting, December 2023) - estimated in-kind contributions (€) for the nine main Additional Activities categories. More detailed information about AAPs and the progress on budget provisions commissioned by EOSC-A Members can be found on EOSC-A website under the tab Monitoring & Reporting in the Section Additional Activities: Planning and reporting⁹.

⁷ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/AAPsurvey2024_28_06_2023_EN.pdf

⁸ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/20220627_AAP_2023_survey_Guidance_materials_v3_IN.pdf

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/monitoring-reporting/>

Table 1. Annual estimated in-kind contributions in Additional Activities, AA provided by EOSC-A Members for year 2024 (AAP 2024 survey). A summary for main AA categories is provided.

AA Category	Estimated annual value per AA category (€)
1. Support to additional R&I	127,228,459.00
2. Scale-up of technologies	16,405,600.00
1. Demonstrators	23,230,890.00
4. Creating new business opportunities	1,110,000.00
5. Training & skills development	36,208,689.00
6. Contribution to the development of new standards, regulations and policies	32,403,032.00
7. Supporting ecosystem development	67,855,321.04
8. Communication, dissemination, awareness raising, citizen engagement	8,264,283.00
9. Other	22,675,962.00
Total:	335,382,236.04

2.2. Additional Activities Report 2022 (AAR 2022)

The EOSC Partnership requires an annual report to be submitted to the Partnership Board documenting the actual in-kind contributions (agreed and provided in the previous year) via the Additional Activities Report, AAR survey. Thus, the objective of the AAR 2022 survey conducted in Q3 2023 by EOSC-A with the support of EOSC Focus was to validate the budget provisions by EOSC-A Members to Additional Activities in 2022. Similar to the AAP 2024 survey, it was conducted on the EUSurvey platform⁶. Eighty-nine members completed the survey, representing twenty-five countries in Europe such as North Macedonia, Norway and Portugal. 52% of respondents came from Research Performing Organisations, 30% were Service Providers, 9% Research Funding Organisations and 9% came from other type of organisations. The categories that EOSC-A members contributed the most were: Category 1- Support to additional R&I planned investment, €127 million: Category 6- Contribution to the development of new standards, regulations and policies, €28 million and Category 7- Supporting ecosystem development, €33 million.

As there was no specific AAP 2022 template, the AAR 2022 survey structure was aligned with that of the AAP 2024 survey to ensure consistency in reporting. It consisted of the same three Sections, but was launched to collect information on the actual in-kind contributions, provided in 2022. The AAR 2022 survey questionnaire is available on the EOSC-A website¹⁰.

Table 2 shows a summary of the AAR 2022 survey results. The actual in-kind contributions (€) for nine main categories of Additional Activities are presented. A total of €292 million was reported, compared to the AAP 2022 forecast of €312 million. Thus, over half of the committed volume of activities in the MoU was already achieved by the end of 2022. Detailed information on the AAR 2022 survey results can be found on the EOSC-A website under the Monitoring & Reporting tab in the Section Additional Activities: Planning and Reporting⁸.

The deviations between planned and actual in-kind contributions for the period between 1 June 2021 and 31 December 2022 have already been presented and discussed in the first biennial Full Monitoring Report¹¹. Figure 1 below summarises these deviations in a simplified way. The following reasons for discrepancies should be highlighted: different activities actually performed compared to planned

¹⁰ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/AAPsurvey2022_14_08_2023_EN26.pdf

¹¹ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/20231212_FMR.pdf

ones; lower/higher number of FTEs; use of different FTE conversion rate; amount prorated into different financial years.

Table 2. Annual actual in-kind contributions in Additional Activities, AA provided by EOOSC-A Members for year 2022 (AAR 2022 survey).

AA Category	Actual annual value per AA category (€)
1. Support to additional R&I	148.478.941,00
2. Scale-up of technologies	11.625.605,00
3. Demonstrators	21.540.346,00
4. Creating new business opportunities	646.350,00
5. Training & skills development	26.343.700,00
6. Contribution to the development of new standards, regulations and policies	28.011.358,00
7. Supporting ecosystem development	33.473.995,00
8. Communication, dissemination, awareness raising, citizen engagement	6.474.084,00
9. Other	15.568.582,94
Total:	292.162.961,94

Figure 1. Comparison of estimated (results from AAP 2022) and actual (results from AAR 2022) annual values (M€) per Additional Activities (AA) category, for the in-kind contributions provided by EOOSC-A Members in the form of AAs from 01/06/2021 to 31/12/2022. The AA categories are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Summarising, in 2023, EOOSC-A in-kind contributions, through the results gathered in the AAR 2022 survey (292 MEUR) as well as the plans for 2023 (383 MEUR) and 2024 (335 MEUR), reached €1 billion, showing impressively the commitment of EOOSC-A members to the goals and objectives of the Partnership (Figure 2). Should the 2022 trend continue for 2023, the EOOSC-A will have already achieved the 10-years-goal commitment after just 2 years. Please note AAP 2021 survey results, although already approved, have not been included in the figures due to the uncertainty about how much of it would be eligible

Additional Activities 2022 to 2024 - MEUR

Figure 2. Planned EOSC-A Members In-kind contributions from AAP surveys (2022-2024) and final (actual) in-kind contributions from AAR 2022 survey.

2.3. Biennial Reporting

According to the MoU¹, the continuous monitoring and reporting by the Partners should be carried out at least annually, with a full reporting every second year (2023, 2025, 2027 for the EOSC Partnership). The biennial full reporting is expected to cover the following points¹:

- Progress of the Co-programmed European Partnership using KPIs and expected scientific, economic and societal impacts (following the Horizon Europe Key Impact Pathways);
- Information on the Partnership's functioning, including openness, transparency, collaboration and synergies with other European Partnerships and initiatives;
- Agreed contributions;
- Investments in operational activities by EOSC-A along with leverage and additional investment mobilised;
- "Impact case studies" showcasing lessons learned and potential follow-up actions.

The biennial reporting process of the Partnership begins with monitoring of indicators common for all Horizon Europe partnerships through the Common Indicators (CI) survey. This is followed by the submission of individual Partnership fiches and the Partnership Full Monitoring Report (FMR) as depicted schematically in Figure 3. The data provided in the CI surveys, Partnerships' fiches and FMRs are used as input for the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR) on the performance of all HE Partnerships, which is published by the EC. The next BMR is expected to be published at the end of March 2024, with subsequent BMRs to be published in 2026 and 2028.

The first CI survey launched as part of the BMR 2024 was conducted in Q3 of 2023 on the EUSurvey platform by the EC. Section 2.3.1 provides a summary of the results of the CI survey submitted by the EOSC-A. In November 2023, the EOSC-A submitted the Partnership Fiche to the EC, as outlined in Section 2.3.2. With the support of the EOSC Focus project, the first biennial FMR 2024¹¹ of the EOSC Partnership has already been submitted for the period 1 June 2021 – 30 June 2023 and is described in Section 2.3.3.

Figure 3. Biennial reporting process of HE Partnerships.

2.3.1. The Common Indicators Survey

The CI survey evaluates the effectiveness, progress, and impact of HE Partnerships, focusing on the added value that is generated by the Partnerships compared to alternative policy measures. It is used for monitoring and evaluating the HE Partnerships' alignment with EU priorities and objectives. In September 2023, the EOOSC-A with the support of EOOSC Focus WP4 participated in the CI survey for the BMR 2024, covering aspects like additionality and directionality, international visibility and positioning, openness and transparency, coherence and synergies and thematic focus.

The BMR 2024 CIs survey questionnaire, available on the EOOSC-A website¹², consisted of six Sections:

- Section I: 'Additionality and directionality',
- Section II: 'International visibility and positioning',
- Section III: 'Openness and transparency',
- Section IV: 'Coherence and synergies',
- Section V: 'Thematic focus of the BMR 2024',
- Section VI: 'Additional data for the mid-term evaluation of Horizon Europe - Efficiency'.

In Sections I-IV, eleven Common Indicators were reported, addressing financial contributions, broader investments, funding alignment with EU priorities, collaboration with non-European actors, and more¹². The indicators used were both quantitative and qualitative, and some included the presentation of success stories and practical examples. Section V assessed the Partnership's alignment with European strategic autonomy/technological sovereignty by asking two additional questions. Section VI comprised three questions focusing on efficiency, a criterion used in the interim evaluation of Horizon Europe.

The results of CIs survey submitted by the EOOSC-A for the BMR 2024 are summarised below:

- Progress data on in-kind contributions by August 2023 amounted to € 532.691.897,91. It should be noted that €500 million was committed for the whole duration of the Partnership (until 2030).

¹² https://eoosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CommonIndicatorsSurvey_EOOSC-A_2023.pdf

Please note that the reported amount of €532.691.897,91 is the sum of validated and estimated in-kind contributions. At the time the CI survey 2023 was submitted, EOSC-A members were still in the process of submitting final 2022 figures. The breakdown of the contributions reads as follow:

AAP 2022 Total In-kind contributions for the period Jan 22 to Dec 22	275.459.269,34 €	
Of those final contributions	246.676.741,34 €	90%
Of those estimated contributions (awaiting for EOSC-A members to make final submissions)	28.782.528,00 €	10%

For the period Jan 23 to Aug 23, we have prorated AAP 2023 estimated contributions:
257.232.628,57 €

Total amount, partners other than the Union, committed in kind to this partnership by August 2023:
532.691.897,91 €

- The above contributions in kind come from the members of the EOSC Association. However, in all the Member States and Associated Countries the contribution to EOSC related activities that fall within the scope of the SRIA is much larger. Since less than 20% of the Research Performing Organisations is a member of the Association it is safe to at least multiply the in kind contributions mentioned above by a factor of 5 (five). Thus, the estimated total additional investment (beyond the contributions from partners) generated by August 2023 was approximately €2.7 billion (approx. 540 mln EUR x 5).
- The Partnership is focused on digitalization objectives, planning to allocate 100% of its budget towards these goals. By August 2023, 65% of this digitalisation investment target was achieved.
- The Partnership plans to invest 7% of its overall budget into activities aimed at creating linkages and collaboration with international organisations and entities in non-EU countries.
- The EOSC-A has already achieved international visibility and collaboration. Currently EOSC-A has 256 members (including both Members and Observers) worldwide, representing countries from around the world, comprising EU, associated, widening and third countries.
- EOSC-A has focused on increasing its international visibility through various channels, including its website and social media, YouTube, monthly newsletters but also through different events, such as National Tripartite Events, EOSC Symposium and others.
- The Partnership has implemented different measures to ensure openness, transparency, and inclusivity by engaging various stakeholders from different countries and sectors, including Ministries, Research Funding Agencies (RFOs), Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), and private entities.
- EOSC-A financial resources only come from membership fees or from the Union. However, several Members of the EOSC-A use national/regional/structural funds for EOSC-related investments and in-kind contributions.

It was indicated in the Survey that EOSC, as a cross-cutting initiative, is strengthening European technological sovereignty in all six key enabling technologies, which are: advanced manufacturing, advanced (nano)materials, life-science technologies, micro/nano-electronics and photonics, artificial intelligence, and security and connectivity technologies. EOSC key elements to increase Europe's technological sovereignty include developing trustworthy research infrastructures, defining and respecting access rules, and enhancing FAIR research data management skills.

2.3.2. The EOSC Partnership Fiche

The EOSC Partnership Fiche, included in the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR), aims to provide an introduction to the Partnership and outlines its essential specific objectives in relation to broader societal objectives. It offers a comprehensive and detailed overview of the vision, mission, objectives, the Partnership-Specific Impact Pathways (PSIPs), main Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and thematic content with success stories/examples.

With the support of EOSC Focus WP4, the BMR 2024 - EOSC Partner Fiche was submitted by EOSC-A to an EC-nominated Expert advisor, in October 2023. Amendments were requested by the Expert, which were carried out in consultation between the EOSC Association and the EC DG.RTD.A.4 Unit. The amendment included the revision of the EOSC Partnership Specific Impact Pathways (PSIPs) and of the choice of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that would better support the monitoring of the Partnership's impact. The reviewed document was submitted to the EOSC Partnership Board, for the meeting of December 2023, while the review process was going through the last iterations with the Expert reviewer. Although the document was consensually agreed upon, the Partnership Board decided to postpone the approval of BMR2024, to the new year, via a written procedure, as soon as the review process would complete.

For the BMR - Partnership Fiche each Partnership develops its own PSIPs to guide monitoring and evaluation activities. The PSIPs use a "strategy mapping" approach that starts from resources and actions to outcomes and impacts, establishing causal links between them. Partnership-specific KPIs are set for each dimension. While KPIs related to resources and actions focus on managerial aspects, those linked with outputs and impacts depict expected short-, medium-, and longer-term results. These can be translated into impacts on science, economy, and society. PSIPs serve as the basis for the partnership storyline, incorporating partnership-specific KPIs that also align with various categories of Horizon Europe Key Impact Pathways (KIPs).

To understand how the EOSC Partnership vision contributes to societal challenges, the PSIPs from the previous version of BMR was refined¹³ to better align with the Partnership-specific KPIs and to better reflect on the current situation. The resulting strategy map provided in the submitted BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche is shown in Figure 4. In addition, baselines, current results and future targets for selected Partnership-specific KPIs reported in the submitted BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche are presented in Table 3. The baseline values for KPIs were surveyed in October 2022, and refer to the year 2021. These KPIs were later validated for the EOSC FMR 2024¹¹.

With respect to the PSIPs, the selected KPIs and their 2021 baseline values (reported in D.4.2⁵), return the picture of a resourceful environment, with institutional policies on data sharing and reuse, either aligned with EU priorities or progressing in this direction. The partners demonstrate an advanced 'EOSC-readiness' in terms of documented standards and protocols for data sharing and reuse, and

¹³ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/eosc_bmr2022.pdf

progressing rapidly towards an immediate open access to publications. On the other hand, the core functions of the Minimum Viable EOSC still need to be implemented (the EOSC EU Node is planned to become operational in the second half of 2024), and the EOSC Interoperability Framework is still fragmented. The expected impact is starting to materialise in terms of making Open Science the new norm, with Research Infrastructures acting as champions, and EU Member States beginning to insert the Open Science dimension in their educational curriculum. The fuller impact of the EOSC initiative can only materialise once the EOSC EU Node is operational and with a federation of service providers and users benefiting from it.

Figure 4. EOSC Partnership-Specific Impact Pathways (PSIPs) reported in the BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche. Please note that this EOSC Partnership Fiche has been submitted to the EC and is being prepared for publication, in Spring 2024, by the EC’s Partnership Coordination Unit.

A selection of impact case studies was also provided. The impact case studies reported in the BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche will be incorporated into the EOSC Macro-Roadmap¹⁴, with additional information available in Section 3.1 of this Deliverable.

Table 3. Table of KPIs reported in the BMR 2024 -EOSC Partnership Fiche. Please note that this EOSC Partnership Fiche has been submitted to the EC and is being prepared for publication, in Spring 2024, by the EC's Partnership Coordination Unit.

KPI Name	Measure-ment Unit	Baseline	Target 2023	Target 2025	Ambition >2027
Resources (input), processes and activities					
The EOSC EU Node is operational and a growing number of EOSC core functions are discoverable	# of EOSC core functions that are discoverable through the EOSC EU Node	0	N/A	4	6
Metadata are increasingly available for public research data sets	% of EOSC-A RFOs that require (meta)data sharing and incentivise data re-use	67% data sharing, 50% data re-use	N/A	70%	80%
Members' policies adopt Open Science principles and encourage Open Science best practises	% of EOSC-A members that request FAIR in project design via data management plans	40%	70%	75%	80%
Outcomes					
The EOSC Interoperability Framework is adopted by major EU RIs	# of Research Infrastructures adopting the EOSC Interoperability Framework	0 Status: .https://zenodo.org/records/8109528 .https://zenodo.org/records/8399710	5	8	10
Publications from EOSC-A members are immediately available in open access	% of open access publication-record, per year	49%	70%	75%	80%
Thematic European Research Infrastructures have documented standards and protocols for data sharing and re-use.	% of major Research Infrastructures with documented standards and protocols	83%	60%	70%	80%
Impacts					
Open Science is the new norm: i) A growing number of major Research Infrastructures (as a proxy for all major scientific disciplines) have relevant data and services indexed through EOSC ii) A growing number of national education systems recognise curricula for data stewards	# of scientific disciplines (Frascati Nomenclature-Level 1), in major Research Infrastructures, that have relevant data and services indexed through EOSC.	5 from the 6 major disciplines	4	5	All major scientific disciplines have relevant data and services indexed through EOSC
	# of countries where educational curricula with an Open Science dimension were offered	6 (CZ, GE, NL, IE, SK, HR)	5	7	10

In this table, the baseline values were obtained from the EOSC partnership Monitoring Framework KPI survey of October 2022, referring to the year 2021. A colour code was applied: green for KPIs achieved; orange for KPIs on track; red for underachieving KPIs.

2.3.3. The EOSC Full Monitoring Report (FMR)

In order to minimise reporting fatigue, the EC decided to avoid asking for an annual simplified Full Report, as initially planned. Instead, the EC has requested a complete Full Monitoring Report (FMR) every two years. This report is aligned, both in terms of content and of timelines, with the BMR – Partnership Fiche and with the BMR - Common Indicators survey. Therefore, no additional information is requested in the FMR other than the information coming from those two reports, which are due at the same time of the year, in the final quarter.

At its 5th meeting on 6 December 2023, the EOSC Partnership Board approved the first biennial EOSC Partnership Full Monitoring Report. The report, titled *First biennial Full Report of the Co-programmed European Partnership EOSC for the period 01/06/2021-30/06/2022*¹⁴, is available on the EOSC-A website. Approval by DG-RTD A.4's Common Missions & Partnerships Service is still pending.

The FMR 2024 supplemented the BMR 2024 - CI survey and the BMR 2024 - Partnership Fiche by providing information on the additionality (contribution by the EOSC-A Members), directionality (progress towards the objectives) and functioning of the Partnership. It also provided examples of impact case studies, as committed to in the EOSC Partnership MoU. The reported impact case studies are planned for implementation into the EOSC Macro-Roadmap¹⁴. Therefore, more information is described in Section 3.1 of this Deliverable.

3. Impact Assessment

As outlined in the MoU, the periodic reporting from Co-Programmed European Partnership (including the EOSC Partnership) should include “structured and representative ‘impact case studies’ that will be used to highlight lessons learned from specific projects/ activities, their drivers and barriers to impact, and their possible follow-up with the appropriate instruments...”¹.

As described in the above Sections, the monitoring of in-kind contributions to Additional Activities performed by EOSC-A Members is carried out annually via the AAP and AAR surveys. In addition, these surveys also collect case studies with a detailed description of a particularly EOSC-relevant impact case study that can be publicly showcased in the EOSC Macro-Roadmap, developed by EOSC-A with the support of EOSC Focus project as described in Section 3.1. The representative impact case studies reported in the BMR 2024 EOSC Partnership Fiche and in the EOSC FMR 2024 were also selected using data from AAP/AAR surveys as outlined in Section 3.1.

3.1. EOSC Macro-Roadmap

The EOSC Partnership Macro-Roadmap¹⁴, conceived and developed within EOSC Focus, is an online tool made available to EOSC stakeholders to aid in visualising the implementation of EOSC over time and across SRIA objectives. Development of the EOSC Macro-Roadmap and its data has continued steadily since its launch in September 2023. WP4's contribution to it, with the planned integration of the EOSC Partnership Additional Activities, in the form of use cases, case studies and good/best practices, is in progress, with the preparation of a template for the collection of cases. The mining of examples from AAR 2022 (followed by AAR 2023 once completed in September 2024) has already started. The AA cases will become included once the EOSC Macro-Roadmap user interface is upgraded. These cases will also be published in the database on the EOSC-A website that will contain

¹⁴ <https://eosc.eu/roadmap>

different filters such as country, target group, SRIA objective, type of result and EOSC Macro-Roadmap area. Each example will have a dedicated webpage with a downloadable pdf/print output.

Working on the EOSC Macro-Roadmap concept, impact case studies reported in the BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche and in the EOSC FMR 2024 are also planned for implementation into the EOSC Macro-Roadmap. Representative impact case studies reported in both, the BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche and the EOSC FMR 2024, were selected from the AAP 2023 survey results¹⁵ approved by the 4th Partnership Board meeting in December 2022. Their selection would especially support the narration of the required thematic foci, i.e., how the EOSC Partnership contributes to: i) the technological sovereignty of Europe; and: ii) to the international visibility and positioning of Europe as a partner in the six Key Enabling Technologies (KETs), of which security and connectivity technologies would be applicable to EOSC.

The choice of cases for the BMR 2024 - Partnership Fiche from both HE projects and EOSC-A Members' Additional Activities, was agreed between EOSC-A and the EC, and articulated as impactful examples of EOSC contribution to: i) the response to the COVID-19 pandemic (the European COVID-19 Data Platform¹⁶, the Galaxy Project¹⁷, the Virus Outbreak Data Network – VODAN¹⁸) and ii) global astronomical challenges (CosmoHub¹⁹). The EOSC FMR¹¹ also included four impact case studies, two^{16,17} of which were reported in the BMR 2024 – EOSC Partnership Fiche, while the other two were new from AAR 2022: Sustainability of the SSH Open Marketplace²⁰ and Data Steward Network (University of Bologna, IT)²¹. For more information on these impact case studies, please refer to the EOSC FMR 2024¹¹ available on the EOSC-A website.

Simultaneously, discussions with the EOSC Steering Board (SubGroup A, Monitoring) and EOSC Future project (WP2) were conducted to ensure alignment of scope and activities, particularly regarding the categorization of use cases. It was agreed that the EOSC-SB_A would focus on national-scale initiatives. EOSC-SB_A also agreed to give consideration to the definitions, proposed by EOSC-A, for the terms: 'use case', 'good/best practice' and 'case study', in order to ensure alignment of practices, which would facilitate the exploitation of those cases in a single joint monitoring system, to eventually synergistically contribute to the impact assessment of the EOSC initiative.

3.2. HE EOSC Impact Working Group

The HE EOSC Impact Working Group kicked off with an online meeting on 31 May 2023. During this first meeting, two recent deliverables of EOSC Focus WP4 were presented: D4.1 'Selection of KPIs to be reported by Horizon Europe projects of the INFRAEOSC calls' & D4.2 'Annual Report Published by the EOSC-A & Monitoring Framework Revision (first release)'. During the meeting, discussions with project representatives were initiated.

The discussion focused on scoping the WG activity, especially exploring how EOSC Focus could support the demonstration of the EOSC value-added with examples of impactful good practices, case

¹⁵ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231211_AAP2023-for-web_1_omoo.pdf

¹⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/the-european-covid-19-data-platform>

¹⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41587-021-01069-1>

¹⁸ <https://www.vodan-totafrica.info/vodan-africa.php?i=1&a=about-vodan-africa;>
[https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ggn2.10050;](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ggn2.10050) <https://worldfair-project.eu>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ascom.2020.100391>

²⁰ bit.ly/47uf04l

²¹ <https://www.unibo.it/en/research/open-science/open-science>

studies and use cases. A definition of these terms was agreed and encapsulated into a document, along with a template for the collection of information. The examples would be nested into the EOSC Macro-Roadmap and contribute to a database of cases to demonstrate EOSC's added value, with the benefit to facilitate the projects in showcasing their impact in an easily consumable way, while demonstrating the added value of EOSC.

In the second semester of 2023, the idea of delivering the EOSC Winter School 2024 took form and a session on the "Sustainable Exploitation of HE projects' Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for Impact" was planned. The concept of a methodology aimed at supporting the HE projects in planning the sustainable exploitation of their KER was presented to the HE Impact WG to be further discussed during the Winter School. A full description of this work will be presented in deliverable D4.4.

The HE EOSC Impact Working Group is represented in the EOSC Forum web platform, with 25 members.

4. Reflections for the future / lessons learned

- The EOSC Focus project has played a crucial role in supporting the EOSC-A in its monitoring and reporting activities, contributing to established routines within the EOSC Partnership. However, streamlining reporting processes could contribute to efficiency and minimise reporting fatigue for EOSC-A members, so the EOSC Focus project plans to explore ways of aligning EOSC monitoring efforts, with the aim of contributing to the development of a consistent EOSC monitoring and reporting structure.
- The AAP 2024 survey and AAR 2022 report were conducted in Q3 2023. As the summer and holiday season affected respondents' responsiveness, the AAP 2025 survey and AAR 2023 report are scheduled for Q2 2024.
- The common indicators survey requests information regarding the types of funding supporting the deployment of the Additional Activities. This information was not collected so far, as it was not requested by the EC template for AAP monitoring and reporting issued in 2021. In order to provide this information when requested in the next iteration of the CI survey, a request to describe the funding types will accompany the next AAP survey. A suggestion should be delivered to the EOSC Steering Board to also incorporate this dimension in the National Contributions survey questionnaire.
- In the BMR 2024, the Partnership Specific Impact Pathways were adapted from the previous release of the report to reflect on the evolution of the EOSC development; the dynamism of EOSC development strategy shall to be taken into account also for the revision of Key Performance Indicators of the EOSC Partnership Monitoring Framework.
- The HE Impact Working Group demonstrated a real appetite for a session on the "Sustainable Exploitation of HE projects' Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for Impact" at the EOSC Winter School held in Thessaloniki (Greece) in January 2024. This provides WP4 and the EOSC-Association with a strong mandate to insert this kind of education and training activities.
- While the EOSC implementation progresses dynamically, the governance and sustainability pathways of this initiative are being revised. This creates uncertainties in the research community, highlighting a difficulty in designing clear exploitation pathways for their project's KERs, until these aspects are clarified.
- Given that EOSC is a complex, cross-cutting initiative, providing solutions for diverse research communities, it is crucial to represent the Partnership performance not only quantitatively, but also qualitatively, with exemplary case studies. Such an approach can convey the diversity of the

EOSC landscape and promote good and best practices, as well as facilitate the scalability and replicability of initiatives and activities that offer cutting-edge opportunities for advancing science.

5. References

No	Description/Link
R1	EOSC Association (2022), Memorandum of Understanding for the Co-programmed European Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC_Memorandum_30_July_2021.pdf
R2	EOSC Association (2023), Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (Version 1.2) https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf
R3	GO FAIR (2016), FAIR Principles https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/
R4	EOSC Association (2022), The EOSC Partnership Monitoring Framework https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/Monitoring%20Framework.pdf
R5	EOSC Association (2023), Deliverable 4.2 (Pending REA Approval), Annual Report Published by EOSC-A & Monitoring Framework Revision (First release) https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20230517_D4.2_3_GS_PendingREA.pdf
R6	EUSurvey platform https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome
R7	EOSC Association (2023), EOSC ASSOCIATION Contributions to additional activities 2024 SURVEY - survey questionnaire https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/AAPsurvey2024_28_06_2023_EN.pdf
R8	EOSC Association (2023), HE EOSC PARTNERSHIP Additional Activities Plan 2024 Survey guidance materials https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/20220627_AAP_2023_survey_Guidance_materials_v3_IN.pdf
R9	EOSC-Association, EOSC-A website, subpage: Monitoring & Reporting https://eosc.eu/monitoring-reporting/
R10	EOSC Association (2023), EOSC ASSOCIATION Contributions to additional activities 2022 SURVEY - survey questionnaire https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/AAPsurvey2022_14_08_2023_EN26.pdf
R11	EOSC Association (2023), First biennial Full Report of the Co-programmed European Partnership EOSC for the period 01/06/2021 - 30/06/2023 https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/20231212_FMR.pdf
R12	European Commission (2023), Common Indicator survey for the partnerships who responded to the BMR 2022 https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CommonIndicatorsSurvey_EOSC-A_2023.pdf
R13	EOSC Association (2022), PARTNERSHIP FICHE: EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD in PERFORMANCE OF EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIPS, BIENNIAL MONITORING REPORT 2022 ON PARTNERSHIPS IN HORIZON EUROPE https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/eosc_bmr2022.pdf
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R19	P. Tallada, J. Carretero, J. Casals, C. Acosta-Silva, S. Serrano, M. Caubet, F.J. Castander, E. César, M. Croce, M. Delfino, M. Eriksen, P. Fosalba, E. Gaztañaga, G. Merino, C. Neissner, N. Tonello, CosmoHub: Interactive exploration and distribution of astronomical data on Hadoop, <i>Astronomy and Computing</i> 32 (2020) 100391 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ascom.2020.100391
R20	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, DARIAH ERIC, The social Sciences and Humanities Open Market – a discovery portal bit.ly/47uf04l
R21	Data Steward Network (University of Bologna, IT) https://www.unibo.it/en/research/open-science/open-science

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author	ORCID ID
v.1	19/12/2024 and 09/01/2024	Draft of the table of contents and presentation of ideas as for the structure of the document	Monika Góral-Kurbiel (NCN), Ilaria Nardello (EOSC-A), Patricia Cabrerizo Padilla (EOSC-A), Aneta Pazik-Aybar (NCN)	Monika Góral-Kurbiel: 0009-0007-0416-7886 Ilaria Nardello: 0002-7294-8867 ; Aneta Pazik-Aybar: 0000-0003-0503-5459
v.1.1	13/02/2024	Overview of first draft of introduction, methodology, results, tables, discussion and content writing started	Monika Góral-Kurbiel (NCN), Ilaria Nardello (EOSC-A), Patricia Cabrerizo Padilla (EOSC-A), Aneta Pazik-Aybar (NCN)	
v.1.2	20/02/2024	Further discussion following EOSC Focus Management Board's recommendations and writing continued	Monika Góral-Kurbiel (NCN), Ilaria Nardello (EOSC-A), Patricia Cabrerizo Padilla (EOSC-A), Aneta Pazik-Aybar (NCN)	
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